

Design guidelines for Gr-MoS₂ based DS-FETs[☆]

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ABSTRACT

As the development of Dirac-Source Field-Effect Transistors (DS-FETs) progresses, there is an increasing need for a robust, flexible, and agile simulation framework capable of evaluating device performance across a range of operating conditions. This work addresses that need by coupling a two-dimensional (2D) Poisson solver with a quantum transport model under the ballistic transport regime. This simulation approach is employed to analyze the electrical characteristics of a DS-FET realized with the heterojunction of graphene and monolayer MoS₂. In addition, the impact of gate-to-channel alignment on device performance is systematically investigated. Simulation results underscore the critical role of full gate overlap with the semiconducting region and substantiate the feasibility of DS-FETs based on these two materials.

1. Introduction

With power consumption emerging as a major constraint of modern electronic systems, steep-slope devices have gained considerable research interest. These devices present a notable advantage by achieving a subthreshold swing (SS) below the thermionic limit of 60 mV/dec at room temperature, thereby surpassing the conventional Boltzmann limit. This characteristic facilitates the downscaling of supply voltage in integrated circuits while maintaining adequate performance levels.

Among the various proposals leveraging different transport mechanisms and materials [1], the Dirac-Source Field-Effect Transistor (DS-FET) has emerged as one of the most promising candidate [2]. The transistor exploits the unique band structure of Dirac materials in the source contact to filter the injection of high-energy electrons into the channel consisting of a semiconductor material. Since electron injection is still thermal, DS-FETs can provide an ON-state current comparable to that of conventional MOSFETs, unlike what happens in Tunnel-FETs, for example. This approach allows the leakage current to be reduced while maintaining a high drive current, thus improving the ON/OFF current ratio. Due to their excellent scalability, DS-FETs based on two-dimensional (2D) materials have attracted considerable research interest [3,4]. In particular, monolayer MoS₂, a semiconductor with a relatively large bandgap, is well-suited to suppress direct source-to-drain tunneling, while graphene—the Dirac material—attracts many interest because of its impressive mobility [5]. Moreover, the two materials can be seamlessly integrated through a Van der Waals heterojunction.

This study builds upon previous work presented in [6], extending the analysis of the band profile. Specifically, the calculation now includes not only the conduction band of the semiconductor but also the

Dirac energy of the graphene, resulting in a comprehensive band profile of the entire DS-FET structure. This approach eliminates the need for the fixed-barrier approximation previously used in [4]. The obtained band profiles are then employed to compute the transmission probability under the ballistic transport assumption. Furthermore, unlike in [6], the tunneling probability is now evaluated using a quantum transport model, providing a more accurate representation of the device behavior. In addition, the impact of gate misalignment with respect to the channel is explored by simulating DS-FETs with different geometries. The analysis reveals that device performance remains optimal as long as the gate completely covers the semiconductor channel region.

It is worth noting that, in this work, ballistic transport is assumed to provide an upper bound on device performance and enable rapid design-space exploration. While this assumption neglects scattering effects – relevant for channels longer than 10 nm – it allows for qualitative insight at a much lower computational cost than full-scale transport models. Moreover, contact resistances, Fermi-level pinning, interface trap effects, and phenomena at the heterojunction, such as charge transfer mechanisms, and interface states, are not included in the present model, which focuses on the basic features of the DS-FET to assess the best performance achievable by this device. Although simplified, the present model allows to qualitatively estimate the device behavior at a significantly lower computational cost compared to more complex ab-initio methods.

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Fig. 1. Band profile of the DS-FET in the transport direction for various values of V_{GS} . As schematized in the upper part, the red dashed vertical lines highlight the position of the gate, the black one represents the heterojunction coordinate, and the blue one sets the end of the p-doped graphene region. The doping of the semiconductor drain region is $4.3 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and that of the graphene source is $6.8 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. A 1-nm-thick SiO_2 layer is employed as gate oxide. Note that, the gate voltage affects also the Dirac energy in the undoped graphene region next to the semiconductor channel. This effect is beneficial for the performance, since it reduces the height of the barrier at the heterojunction.

2. Band profile calculation

Starting from what is illustrated in [6], where the electrostatics of the semiconductor channel is investigated under the assumption of an infinitely thin 2D charge layer, here the discussion is expanded so as to include also the semi-metallic source region.

The Dirac material employed in the DS-FET under study is graphene. It consists of carbon atoms arranged in a 2D honeycomb crystal lattice which can be considered as two equivalent sublattices. Thanks to this property, the behavior of charge carriers in graphene can be modeled using the Dirac equation, resulting in a linear energy–momentum dispersion relation with respect of \mathbf{k} ,

$$E(\mathbf{k}) - E_D = \hbar v_F |\mathbf{k}|, \quad (1)$$

where E_D is the Dirac energy, \hbar the reduced Planck constant, and $v_F = 1 \times 10^8 \text{ cm/s}$ the Fermi velocity of graphene. From (1) it is possible to extract the density of states

$$D(E) = \frac{2|E - E_D|}{\pi \hbar^2 v_F^2}, \quad (2)$$

that is used to compute the charge carrier densities. Proceeding this way, the electron density per unit surface in graphene is calculated as in [7], namely

$$\begin{aligned} n_{Gr} &= \int_{E_D}^{+\infty} \frac{2(E - E_D)}{\pi \hbar^2 v_F^2} \left[1 + \exp\left(\frac{E - E_{FS}}{k_B T}\right) \right]^{-1} dE \\ &= \frac{2(k_B T)^2}{\pi \hbar^2 v_F^2} \Gamma(2) \mathcal{F}_1(\mu_{FS} - \eta_D), \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

with $\eta_D = E_D/k_B T$ being the normalized Dirac energy, $\mu_{FS} = E_{FS}/k_B T$ the normalized source Fermi energy, k_B the Boltzmann constant, and

$T = 300 \text{ K}$ the temperature, while $\Gamma(2) = (2 - 1)! = 1$ is the gamma function and $\mathcal{F}_1(x)$ represents the Fermi–Dirac integral of order 1, defined, for an arbitrary order α , as

$$\mathcal{F}_\alpha(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} \int_0^\infty \frac{\xi^\alpha}{1 + \exp(\xi - x)} d\xi. \quad (4)$$

A similar expression can be stated for the hole density

$$\begin{aligned} p_{Gr} &= \int_{-\infty}^{E_D} \frac{2(E_D - E)}{\pi \hbar^2 v_F^2} \left[1 + \exp\left(\frac{E_{FS} - E}{k_B T}\right) \right]^{-1} dE \\ &= \frac{2(k_B T)^2}{\pi \hbar^2 v_F^2} \Gamma(2) \mathcal{F}_1(\eta_D - \mu_{FS}). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Note that, charge carriers are supposed to be in equilibrium with the source contact. The total charge is then the sum of hole and electron contributions $\rho = q(p - n)$, with q the elementary charge.

As a first approximation, the heterojunction between the two materials can be considered to create a barrier corresponding to the difference in their electron affinities. In the case of graphene and MoS_2 , this difference is $\chi_{Gr} - \chi_{\text{MoS}_2} = 0.4 \text{ eV}$ [4].

In Fig. 1 the complete band profile, i.e. the Dirac energy and the conduction band, of the transistor along the transport direction x for some values of the gate voltage is shown. In the upper part of the image, a sketch of the device structure helps to identify the various regions: from the left, a p-doped graphene region, an intrinsic graphene region, an intrinsic MoS_2 region, and a n-doped MoS_2 region. Additionally, the red dashed lines highlight the position of the gate, the blue one delimits the p-doped graphene region, and the black one shows the coordinate of the heterojunction. The transistor is 40 nm long, divided in four regions of equal length. The gate oxide is composed of a layer of 1 nm of SiO_2 ($\epsilon_{ox} = 3.9 \epsilon_0$). The doping level of the semiconductor drain region is $4.3 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, and that of the p-graphene source is $6.8 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. This last one enables the energy filtering effect by properly aligning the Dirac cone with respect to the conduction band. It is worth noting that, in the undoped graphene region the Dirac energy varies with the gate voltage V_{GS} , reducing the barrier height and enhancing the ON-state current by lowering the barrier $\phi_{SB} = E_{C0} - E_{FS}$, with E_{C0} being the conduction band of MoS_2 at the beginning of the channel, and $E_{FS} = 0 \text{ eV}$ the source Fermi level. The latter effect is not highlighted in [4], where ϕ_{SB} is considered to be fixed with respect to V_{GS} .

3. Current estimation

As in [6], the electron current is computed within the ballistic approximation using the Landauer formalism. The analysis takes advantage of the fact that, within the relevant energy range, the number of modes in graphene is lower than that of the semiconductor. This results in the following expression:

$$I_{DS} \simeq \frac{2q}{h} \int_{E_c}^\infty M_{Gr}(E) T(E) f(E - E_{FS}) dE, \quad (6)$$

where $\tilde{E}_c = \min\{E_c\}$ is the minimum value of the conduction band, $M_{Gr}(E) = W 2|E - E_{D0}|/\pi \hbar v_F$ the number of modes in graphene, $T(E)$ the tunneling probability, and $f(E - E_{FS})$ the Fermi charge distribution function at the source contact. Note that the drain potential is assumed to be sufficiently high to have no effect on the current. In Eq. (6), the Dirac energy at source $E_{D0} = E_D(x = 0)$ is fixed by the doping level and is equal to $E_{D0} \simeq 0.3 \text{ eV}$. This is a critical point, as it highlights graphene's function as a filter for high-energy electrons.

The transmission probability is estimated using the quantum transmitting boundary method (QTBM) [8]. This approach implies the solution of the Schrödinger equation and allows one to extract not only the transmission and reflection coefficients, but the full wave function in the device region. After introducing the hypothesis of ideal Klein tunneling transmission at the graphene pn junction [9], the transistor can be modeled as comprising two semi-infinite contacts connected to the device's semiconductor channel. Consequently, two key implications

Fig. 2. Local density of states (LDOS) in the semiconductor section and spectral current, in green, of the DS-FET for $V_{GS} = 0.1$ V.

arise: first, the Hamiltonian of the entire system simplifies to that of the semiconductor, which can be modeled using the parabolic effective mass approximation and the stationary Schrödinger equation

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m^*} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} + E_C(x) \right] w = Ew; \quad (7)$$

Second, because the potential remains constant in the regions adjacent to the 2D semiconductor, the solutions in these semi-infinite regions take the form of plane waves

$$\begin{cases} w(x) = \exp(ik_1x) + B_1 \exp(-ik_1x), & \text{for } x < x_1, \\ w(x) = A_2 \exp(ik_2x), & \text{for } x > x_2, \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

with $k_{1,2} = \sqrt{2m^*[E - E_C(x_{1,2})]/\hbar^2}$ and x_1, x_2 being the coordinates of the heterojunction and of the drain respectively. Subsequently, the device region is discretized and the Schrödinger equation is solved with the finite difference method (FDM), exploiting (8) and their derivative as boundary conditions. Once the wave function is obtained, the transmission probability can be computed as $T = A_2 k_2/k_1$.

Fig. 2 shows the local density of states (LDOS) in the semiconductor channel and the spectral current of the DS-FET in Fig. 1 with $V_{GS} = 0.1$ V, computed via the QTBM. The absence of states below the channel barrier confirms that no source-to-drain tunneling occurs. This is due to the relatively high effective mass of monolayer MoS₂, $m^* = 0.51 m_0$ [4]. Examining the current, the negative peak observed at $E = E_{D0}$ is attributed to the filtering effect of graphene at the source.

Finally, the turn-on characteristics are shown in Fig. 3, where the I-V curve obtained in this study (shown in red) is compared with the curves from [4] (in blue). The inset clearly demonstrates the dependence of E_D on the gate voltage: as V_{GS} increases, the height of the Schottky barrier at the heterojunction, ϕ_{SB} , decreases. This effect is crucial because it enables the transition from the worst case scenario, with $\phi_{SB} = 0.4$ eV at $V_{GS} = -0.1$ V, to a quasi-optimal one, $\phi_{SB} = 0.1$ eV at $V_{GS} = 0.33$ V, thus enabling the sub-60 mV/dec regime. Moreover, in the latter case the red current exceeds the blue one. This is due to the sharp bending of the semiconductor's conduction band immediately after the heterojunction (as shown by the dark blue curve in the inset), which results in a significantly higher transmission probability.

Fig. 3. Turn-on characteristic (red curve) compared with results from [4] (blue curves), where a fixed ϕ_{SB} is considered. Blue circles correspond to gate voltages shown in the inset, which displays a segment of the conduction band at three distinct V_{GS} , each associated with a different ϕ_{SB} . The reduction of the Dirac energy in the intrinsic graphene region decreases the channel barrier height, leading to a higher I_{ON} .

4. Impact of the gate position on performances

Given the complex and multi-step manufacturing process of DS-FETs, it is possible for some devices to be defective. In this work, the focus is on assessing the impact of gate misalignment with respect to the various channel materials/regions on device performance. To achieve this, various configurations are examined, and the results are presented below.

Fig. 4 shows the band profile of the DS-FET at a fixed gate voltage $V_{GS} = 0.4$ V for different gate geometries. The yellow case is the same shown in Fig. 1, where the gate completely overlaps the intrinsic semiconductor region, being L_{2DSC} long, and half of the intrinsic graphene region, being L_{iGr} long. The blue curve represents a scenario where the gate fully overlaps the undoped graphene region, while the pink curve represents the opposite, a case where the gate covers only the semiconductor channel. Finally, a scenario where the gate partially overlaps with the semiconductor channel is considered and denoted by the green configuration. In essence, Fig. 4 illustrates the impact of potential gate misalignment that may occur during the manufacturing process. If the gate is longer than expected, no significant changes appear in the semiconductor conduction band. However, if the gate does not fully cover the undoped semiconductor region, a larger-than-expected barrier forms at the heterojunction.

This effect is reflected in the turn-on characteristics shown in Fig. 5. The significant increase in the barrier at the heterojunction, as seen in the green band profile (Fig. 4), leads to a reduced electron transmission probability and current. In contrast, the pink curve appears unaffected by the larger ϕ_{SB} . This can be attributed to the sharp edges of the barrier [6].

5. Conclusions

In this work a 2D Poisson solver has been coupled with a quantum transport model under the ballistic transport regime. This simulation approach has been employed to analyze the electrical characteristics

Fig. 4. Band profile of the DS-FET at $V_{GS} = 0.4$ V for different lengths of the gate contact L_g . The quantities L_{iGr} and L_{i2DSC} represent the undoped graphene and semiconductor channel length, respectively. The yellow case is the same shown in Fig. 1. The blue case represents a scenario where the gate fully overlaps the undoped graphene region, while the pink case represents the opposite. Of particular importance is the green case, where the gate partially overlaps with the semiconductor channel leading to a longer and higher tunneling barrier.

of a DS-FET realized with the heterojunction of graphene and monolayer MoS₂. The results show a significantly higher ON-state current than previously predicted in [4]. This characteristic, combined with the sub-60 mV/dec regime, supports the viability of 2D DS-FETs as steep-slope devices. Additionally, it is noted that the gate's positioning relative to the various regions of the device could play a critical role in future experimental implementations. Specifically, it was observed that as long as the gate fully covers the semiconductor region of the channel, the device performance remains unaffected.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Tommaso Ugolini: Writing – original draft, Software, Investigation.
Elena Gnani: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Fig. 5. Comparison of the turn-on curves of devices with different gate lengths, as shown in Fig. 4. From the comparison it can be inferred that, as long as the gate contact fully covers the channel region, the current remains almost unchanged. However, when the gate does not overlap the heterojunction, a degradation of the ON-state current is observed due to the longer and higher tunneling barrier.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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